

REN+HOMES

*Resident-centred
methodology for
developing positive
energy residential
buildings*

A structured approach
to co-design energy-aware behaviours in
sustainable households

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European Union

The RENplusHOMES project develops positive-energy buildings where residents play an active role in reaching energy performance targets. This factsheet presents a structured method to engage building users—students, tenants and facility staff—in understanding technologies, co-designing behavioural measures and monitoring their adoption. Through surveys, participatory labs and cross-

site comparison, the method supports residents in being part of the positive stack in the building energy share by co-defining and implementing daily practices that can positively influence the effectiveness of innovative buildings. The aim is to provide organisations with a transferable engagement blueprint for building operations and renovation.

Context & Actors

Positive-energy buildings require well-designed technologies and equally well-supported residents who understand and internalise their functioning. RENplusHOMES' innovations have been applied to four residential building types, thus involving varied user profiles—university dormitories, social housing and multi-tenant buildings. This made resident engagement essential.

Local teams working on the four demonstrators coordinated the setting up of voluntary user groups, organised participatory activities and collected feedback on how occupants understand, use and benefit from the building's systems. Experts provided additional views on architecture, energy systems and social sciences, ensuring that both technical and human factors were addressed.

Approach: listening, understanding, and involving citizens

The method drew on human-centred design.

- +1 Assessment of residents' habits and awareness
- +2 Collaborative activities to create practical roadmaps for the experimentation of new sustainable behaviours
- +3 Evaluation and cross-site learning

Each demonstration site adapted the approach to its context while following shared principles:

This iterative cycle of exploration, planning, experimentation, and assessment allowed trust to be earned, improving transparency, and supporting locally relevant solutions.

Key components:

Impact: what changes

Building managers, public entities and universities gain an operational model to involve occupants in the performance of renovated or newly built positive-energy facilities. The structured engagement cycle helps reduce the gap between expected and actual performance by clarifying how technologies function and what behaviours support efficiency.

Residents develop greater confidence in building systems, understand energy flows better, and actively help towards collective comfort and reduced consumption.

Organisations can reuse the engagement blueprint to support future renovations and frame behaviour-change activities with measurable indicators. The emphasis on comparability across sites enables broader learning for policies on energy-efficient housing and educational facilities.

Results at a Glance

- + Resident surveys provide initial evidence on awareness levels, perceived comfort and self-reported energy practices.
- + Design labs help transform these insights into operational roadmaps that describe behaviour-based measures linked to heating, cooling, ventilation and everyday appliance use, tailored to the needs of residents.
- + Early prototyping shows that residents appreciate simple monitoring tools and clear explanations of how their actions contribute to building performance.
- + Cross-site discussions highlight recurring needs: straightforward interfaces, predictable indoor comfort and guidance that fits daily routines.

Partners & Roles

Project coordination:

RINA Consulting

Lead for resident engagement and co-design

methodology:

SocialFare

Technology and building implementation teams:

Neue Heimat Tirol, Technical University of Cluj
Napoca, Evowall, TalTech

Scientific and advisory contributors:

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